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THE INNOVATION UNIVERSITY®

Stevens Institute of Technology

Stevens Institute for AI

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Stevens Institute of Technology belongs to an exclusive list of the top 25 "Most Innovative Schools" in the US, ranked #69 overall, the second fastest-rising college in the nation among the top 100 national universities. It scores Top 25 for Internships.

The **Stevens Institute for Artificial Intelligence** (SIAI) is an interdisciplinary, tech-driven collaboration of engineering, business, systems and design experts working toward solving pressing global problems in industry and the world.

Stevens Institute for Artificial Intelligence

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Stevens Institute for Artificial Intelligence is composed of more than 50 faculty members from all academic units at Stevens (engineering, business, systems and arts & music) researching a variety of applications in AI and machine learning. SIAI hopes to amplify the impact of its research and analysis through collaborations with industry, government, foundations and academic partners.

READY FOR:

RESEARCHERS

INNOVATORS

OPEN IDEAS

OPEN IDEAS

PROPOSE YOUR OWN IDEA

Submit openly a disruptive idea based on your line of research, product or service. Attract the interest of this US Node.

FOCUS TECHNOLOGY AREAS

AI	Blockchain
Big Data	IoT
5G	Cybersecurity
Cloud/Edge	

KEY APPLICATION SECTORS

Mental Health
Connected Transportation
Smart City

